

First Formal Record of *Toxodera hauseri* Roy, 2009 (Mantodea, Toxoderidae) from Borneo

Andrew Markey

Abstract. The first formal specimen record of *Toxodera hauseri* Roy, 2009 from Sabah, Borneo is documented. This species was previously documented as occurring in the Malay Peninsula, Java, Thailand, and Borneo. The recorded occurrence from Borneo was based solely on a photographic record. This study will confirm the presence of *hauseri* in Borneo through the analysis of a physical specimen that was collected from the island.

The genus *Toxodera* Audinet-Serville, 1837 contains medium to large, highly specialized stick mimicking mantises. Members of this genus possess unique characteristics and are easily distinguished by their pointed compound eyes, foliaceous expansions on the mid and hind femora, and a strongly curved pronotum. There are a total of eight species of *Toxodera*, all of which are distributed in Southeast Asia. Four species are confirmed in Borneo (Roy 2009) where they are restricted to humid old-growth forests, inhabiting the understory. *Toxodera* are seldom ever seen in the wild (Schwarz and Konopik 2014). As a result, many aspects of their ecology are not well known. Furthermore, there are several species where the existence of females has yet to be recorded.

In 2009, the tribe Toxoderini was revised by Roy, who provided keys for identification and added newly described species. *Toxodera hauseri* Roy 2009 was one of the new species described, named in honor of Dr. Bernd Hauser, the former collections manager of the “minor groups” of insects at the Natural History Museum of Geneva (MHNG), the institution where the holotype is deposited. Roy documented the distribution of this species through examination of material from Thailand, West Malaysia, and Java, but did not mention any Bornean material in his research. It wasn’t until a photograph of a live male at the Poring Hot Springs in Sabah was taken by photographer Arthur Anke in 2007 that first evidenced the occurrence of this species in Borneo (Figure 1).

Subsequent to this photograph, in 2015, a dried *Toxodera* Serville, 1837 specimen was collected in North Borneo by the Chaminade Society of France and was obtained by the author through trade. The morphological characters of this specimen were compared with those of *Toxodera* type specimens and other material within the author’s private collection. The specimen was identified based on the keys, descriptions, and illustrations by Roy (2009). The morphology of the genitalia was compared with the *hauseri* paratype that is preserved in MNHN. Pronotum

length is 34 mm long and 4.0 mm wide, with the metazone 28 mm long, strongly arched and streamlined. This analysis confirmed the identification of this specimen as *Toxodera hauseri* Roy, 2009.

FIGURE 1: Male *Toxodera hauseri* seen at the Poring Hot Springs in Sabah, Borneo.© Dr. Arthur Anker.

FIGURE 2: Identifying characteristics of male *Toxodera hauseri* from the Borean specimen. **A.** Anterior view of cranial structures. **B.** Thoracic prozone in dorsal view. **C.** Extension of the 5th tergite. **D.** Femoral foliaceous expansion. **E.** Subgenital plate showing two styli. **F.** Right cercus in dorsal view. **G.** Pinned specimen in dorsal view. Images of genitalia were taken with a microscope lens attached to an iPhone XS. Figures were edited and finalized in Photoshop.

FIGURE3: Specimens of *Toxodera hauseri* in collections. **A.** Paratype male from Malaysia deposited at SMNK. **B.** Paratype male from Thailand deposited at SMNK.

The known geographic distribution of *hauseri* is still limited, as there are only a few collection records (Figure 4). This species is restricted to old-growth forests and inhabits areas beneath the forest canopy. They are seldom seen in the wild. Males are attracted to artificial lights at night. Females remain unknown. The voucher specimen for this study will be donated to the National Museum of Natural History (MNHN), where the male paratype is deposited, so that future research can be conducted.

FIGURE4: Southeast Asia distribution range of *Toxodera hauseri* (red circles).

Material examined. **MALAYSIA**, 31.X. 1977, P. Pfanner, 1 male paratype 3621, coll. MNHN — **MALAYSIA**, Prov. Perak, Taiping, V.1981, leg. H. Steinert, 1 male SMNK — **THAILAND**, Surathani (Ban Don), 9°08 N 99° 19 E, IX.1987, leg. S. Steinke, 1 male SMNK — **MALAYSIA**, Mt. Trusmadi, Sabah, IV.2015, 1 male, coll. A. Markey — **MALAYSIA**, Tapah Hills, Perak, IV.2015, 1 male, coll. A. Markey — **INDONESIA**, Mt. Halimun, West Java, V.2022, 1 male, coll. A. Markey.

Acknowledgements. I would like to thank Roger Roy for his explanation of male and female Mantodea genitalia and verifying the Bornean specimen's sex. I would also like to express my gratitude to Dr. Alexander Riedel and M. Falkenberg of Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde Karlsruhe (SMNK) for their assistance with providing photographs of paratype specimens.

References.

- Audinet-Serville, J. - G. (1837) Nouveau genre d'Horthopteres de la famille des Mantides. Annales de la Societe entomologique de France, 6, 25 - 29.
- Ouwens, P. A. (1913) Eenige weinig bekende Mantis of Roofsprinkhanen van Java. De Tropische Natuur, 9 (2), 122 - 123.
- Roy, R. (2009) Révision des Toxoderini sensu novo (Mantodea, Toxoderinae). Revue suisse de Zoologie, 116 (1), 93–183.
- Saussure, H. de (1869) Essai d'un système des mantides. Mittheilungen der Schweizerischen entomologischen Gesellschaft, 3(2), 49–73.
- Schwarz, Christian & Konopik, Oliver. (2014). An annotated checklist of the praying mantises (Mantodea) of Borneo, including the results of the 2008 scientific expedition to Lanjak Entimau Wildlife Sanctuary, Sarawak. Zootaxa. 3797. 130-68. 10.11646/zootaxa.3797.1.12.
- Werner, F. (1930) Über asiatische Mantideen aus dem naturhistorischen Reichsmuseum in Stockholm. Arkiv for Zoologi, 21 A (34), 1 - 10, pls. 1 - 3.
- Yang, C. (1997) Four new and rare species of mantids from Yunnan China (Insecta: Mantodea). Journal of Yunnan Agricultural University, 12 (4), 227 - 233.